

Rapid Deployment of Speech Processing Systems to New Languages and Domains

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Outline

- The World's Languages
 - 6900 languages – So what?
 - Language Extinction – What can the community do about it?
 - Do we need Speech Processing for all of them?
 - Is this really science – not just retraining on a new language?
- Language Characteristics
 - Written form, scripts, letter-to-sound relationship
 - Issues and Differences between languages
- Challenges for Multilingual Speech Processing
 - Lack of Resources (Money, Data, Technical Support)
 - Lack of Experts
- Solutions
 - SPICE: A Rapid Language Adaptation Server
 - Technologies: Leveraging off GlobalPhone & FestVox
 - Experiments and Results
- Conclusions and Future Work

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Everyone speaks English, why bother?

- Total number of Languages in the world: **6912**
- Language is not only a communication tool but fundamental to cultural identity and empowerment!
- Cultures, ideas, memories transmit ***through language***
- Intellectual issues (e.g. world history)
Practical issues (medical practices)
Literature, ...
Slovakian proverb: “with each newly learned language you acquire a new soul”
- Preserve linguistic diversity! Similar to eco systems (David Crystal)

Increasing Language Diversity in Web

Diversity of Languages in the Internet grows rapidly

- Top-10: 200%, All others: 440%
- Portuguese: 524%
- Arabic: 940%

Internet Usage by World Region

Copyright © 2007, www.internetworldstats.com

Top Ten Languages Used in the Web
(Number of Internet Users by Language)

TOP TEN LANGUAGES IN THE INTERNET	% of all Internet Users	Internet Users by Language	Internet Penetration by Language	Internet Growth for Language (2000 - 2007)	2007 Estimate World Population for the Language
English	31.7 %	365,893,996	17.9 %	157.7 %	2,042,963,129
Chinese	31.7 %	166,001,513	12.3 %	413.9 %	1,351,737,925
Spanish	8.8 %	101,539,204	22.9 %	311.4 %	442,525,601
Japanese	7.5 %	86,300,000	67.1 %	83.3 %	128,646,345
German	5.1 %	58,981,592	61.1 %	112.9 %	96,488,326
French	5.1 %	58,456,702	15.1 %	379.2 %	387,820,873
Portuguese	4.1 %	47,326,760	20.2 %	524.7 %	234,099,347
Korean	3.0 %	34,120,000	45.6 %	79.2 %	74,811,368
Italian	2.7 %	31,481,928	52.9 %	138.5 %	59,546,696
Arabic	2.5 %	28,782,300	8.5 %	940.5 %	340,548,157
TOP TEN LANGUAGES	84.8 %	978,883,995	19.0 %	198.0 %	5,159,187,766
Rest of World Languages	15.2 %	175,474,783	12.4 %	440.3 %	1,415,478,651
WORLD TOTAL	100.0 %	1,154,358,778	17.6 %	219.8 %	6,574,666,417

(*) NOTES: (1) Internet Top Ten Languages Usage Stats were updated for June 30, 2007. (2) Internet Penetration is the ratio between the sum of Internet users speaking a language and the total population estimate that speaks that specific language. (3) The most recent Internet usage information comes from data published by [Nielsen/NetRatings](#), [International Telecommunications Union](#), [Computer Industry Almanac](#), and other reliable sources. (4) World population information comes from the [world gazetteer](#) web site. (5) For definitions and navigation help, see the [Site Surfing Guide](#). (6) Stats may be cited, stating the source and establishing an active link back to [Internet World Stats](#). Copyright © 2007, Miniwatts Marketing Group. All rights reserved.

Currently 6900 Languages, but ...

- Extinction of languages on massive scale
(David Crystal, Spotlight 3/2000)
- Half of all existing languages die out over next century
⇒ On Average: Every two weeks one language dies!
- Survey Feb 1999 from Summer Institute of Linguistics

51 languages with 1 speaker left
28 of those in Australia alone
500 languages with < 500 spks
1500 languages with < 1000 spks
3000 languages with < 10.000
5000 languages with < 100.000
(not safe even for >100.000)

96% of world's languages are
spoken by only 4% of its people

How to save Languages?

Prerequisites and Costs:

- Community itself must want it, Surrounding culture must respect it
- Funding for courses, materials, and teachers, support the community
- Crystal estimates about \$80.000 / year per language
- 3000 endangered languages is about \$700Mio ...
- Foundation of endangered languages (FEL), UNESCO project

How could our community contribute:

- Field Work and Community Outreach
 - Get the tools to the people, i.e. flexible, portable, easy to handle
 - Engage and actively involve native speakers
- Lower the overall costs for data acquisition
 - Automate the solicitation and data collection process
 - Identify language specific aspects and focus
- Reduce the data needs without sacrificing performance
 - Streamline techniques & approaches to perform on small data
 - Reuse language independent aspects of data and models

Why Speech Processing?

Language support is good but why *Speech*?

- Computerization: Speech is *the* key technology
 - ➔ Ubiquitous Information Access: on the go, phone-based
 - ➔ Mobile Devices: Too small and cumbersome for keyboards
- Globalization:
 - ➔ Cross-cultural Human-Human Interaction
 - ➔ Multilingual Communities: EU, South Africa, ...
 - ➔ Humanitarian needs, disaster, health care
 - ➔ Military ops, communicate with local people
 - ➔ Human-Machine Interfaces
 - ➔ People expect speech-driven applications in their mother tongue

⇒ **Speech Processing in multiple Languages**

ML Speech Processing – A Research Issue?

Just retraining on foreign data? - No science!

- New language – new challenges
 - Writing system: different or no script, no vowelization, G-2-P
 - Word segmentation, morphology
 - Sound system: tonals, clicks
- Different Cultures – social factors
 - Trust, access, exposure, background
- Lack of Data and Resources
 - Audio, Transcripts, Pronunciations, Text, parallel bilingual data
- Lack of Experts
 - Technology experts without language expertise
 - Native language experts without technology expertise

**If we can solve the research issues for some languages,
we might help the others along the way!**

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Language Characteristics

- Prosody, Tonality: Stress, Pitch, Length pattern, Tonal contours
(e.g. Mandarin 4, Cantonese 8, Thai & Vietnamese 5)
- Sound system: simple vs very complex sound systems
(e.g. Hawaiian 5V+8C vs. German 17V+3D+22C)
- Phonotactics: simple syllable structure vs complex consonant clusters
(e.g. Japanese Mora-syllables vs. German pf,st,ks)
- Segmentation: Written form separate words by white space?
(NO: Chinese, Japanese, Thai, Vietnamese)
- Morphology: short units, compounds, agglutination
 - English: Natural segmentation into short units – great!
 - German: Compounds – not quite so good
Donau-dampf-schiffahrts-gesellschafts-kapitäns-mütze ...
 - Turkish: Agglutination – loooooong phrases
Osman-lı-laç-tır-ama-yabil-ecek-ler-imiz-den-miş-siniz
behaving as if you were of those whom we might consider not converting into Ottoman

Writing Systems

Writing systems – basic unit is a Grapheme:

Logographic: based on semantic units, grapheme represents meaning

Chinese: >10.000 *hanzi*; Japanese ~7000 *kanji*, Korean to some extent

Phonographic: based on sound units, grapheme represents sound

Segmental: grapheme roughly corresponds to phonemes

Latin (190), Cyrillic (65), Arabic (22) graphemes

Abjads = consonantal segmental phonographic, e.g. Arabic

Syllabic: grapheme represents entire syllable, e.g. Japanese *kana*

Abugidas = mix of segmental and syllabic systems

Featural: elements smaller than phone, e.g. articulatory features

e.g. Korean: ~5600 *gulja*

Segmental: Latin, Cyrillic, Latin&Cyrillic, Greek

Georgian or Armenian

Abjads: Arabic, Arabic&Lat, Hebrew&Arabic

Abugidas: North Indic, South Indic, Ethiopic,

Thaana, Canadian Syllabic

Logographic+syllabic: Pure logographic,

Mixed logographic&syllabaries,

Featural syllabary+lmtd logographic

Featural-alphabetic syllabary

Scripts – Some examples

العربي болгарски català 中国话 hrvatski česky
english ελληνικά עברית हिंदी italiano 日本語
한국어 românește русский српски ภาษาไทย

Scripts of some languages: Arabic, Bulgarian, Catalan, Chinese, Croatian, Czech, English, Greek, Hebrew, Hindi, Italian, Japanese, Korean, Romanian, Serbian, Thai

How many languages do have a written form?

- Omniglot lists about 780 languages that have scripts
- True number might be closer to 1000
(Source Simon Ager, 2007, www.omniglot.com)

→ Logographic scripts, mostly 2 representatives:

- Chinese: ~ 10.000 hanzi,
- Japanese: ~7000 kanji (+ 3 other scripts 😊)

→ Phonographic:

- Korean: ~5600 gulja,
- Arabic, Devanagari, Cyrillic, Roman: ~100 characters

Grapheme-to-Phoneme Relation

Grapheme-to-Phoneme (Letter-to-Sound) Relationship:

Logographic: NO relationship at all

concern for Chinese, Japanese, Korean

Phonographic: segmental: close – far – complicated

e.g. Finnish, Spanish: more or less 1:1, -- English: try „Phydough“

Phonographic: segmental – consonantal

e.g. Arabic: no short vowels written

Phonographic: syllabic

e.g. Thai, Devanagari: C-V flips

➔ Automatic Generation of Pronunciations might get complicated

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Challenges of MLSP

- Lack of Resources: Stochastic approach needs **many** data
 - Hundreds of hours audio recordings and corresponding transcriptions
Audio data \leq 40 languages; Transcriptions take up to 40x real time
 - Pronunciation dictionaries for large vocabularies (>100.000 words)
Large vocabulary pronunciation dictionaries \leq 20 languages
 - Mono- and bilingual text corpora: few language pairs, pivot mostly English
- Algorithms are language independent – MLSP is not!
 - Other Languages bring unseen challenges (segmentation, G2P, etc.)
 - Have we already seen ALL or MOST of the language characteristics?
- Social and Cultural Aspects
 - Non-native speech and language, code switching
 - Combinatorial explosion (domain, speaking style, accent, dialect, ...)
 - Few native speakers at hand for minority (endangered) languages
- Lack of Language Experts
 - Bridge the gap between technology experts and language experts

One Solution: Learning Systems

- ⇒ Intelligent systems that learn a language from the user
- Efficient learning algorithms for speech processing
 - Learning:
 - Interactive learning with user in the loop
 - Statistical modeling approaches
 - Efficiency:
 - Reduce amount of data (save time and costs): at least by factor of 10
 - Speed up development cycles: days rather than months
- ⇒ Rapid Language Adaptation from universal models
- Bridge the gap between language and technology experts
 - Technology experts do not speak all languages in question
 - Native users are not in control of the technology

SPICE

Speech Processing:

Interactive Creation and Evaluation toolkit

- National Science Foundation, Grant 10/2004, 4 years
- Principle Investigator Tanja Schultz
- Bridge the gap between technology experts → language experts
 - Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR),
 - Machine Translation (MT),
 - Text-to-Speech (TTS)
- Develop web-based intelligent systems
 - Interactive Learning with user in the loop
 - Rapid Adaptation of universal models to unseen languages
- SPICE webpage <http://cmuspice.org>

SPICE - Goals

Three main goals:

- Lower the overall costs for data acquisition
 - Automate the solicitation and data collection process
 - Identify language specific aspects and focus
- Reduce the data needs without sacrificing performance
 - Streamline techniques to perform on small data
 - Reuse language independent aspects of data/models
- Field Work and Community Outreach
 - Get the tools to the people, i.e. flexible, portable, easy to handle
 - Engage and actively involve native speakers

Welcome to SPICE

Getting started

SPICE is a web-based system for building an end-to-end speech system (including Automatic Speech Recognition and Text-To-Speech) in your own language.

Existing Users

Login with your account:

Login

Password

New Users

Create a new account:

Login

Password

Re-type
Password

Email

Build Your System

[Text and prompt selection](#) [\(help\)](#)

[Audio collection](#) [\(help\)](#)

[Phoneme selection](#) [\(help\)](#)

[Grapheme-to-phoneme rules](#) [\(help\)](#)

build language model first

[Lexicon pronunciation creation](#) [\(help\)](#)

build language model first

[Build acoustic model](#) [\(help\)](#)

[Build language model](#) [\(help\)](#)

[Create ASR system](#)

[Create speech synthesis voice](#)

User: [TanjaSchultz](#) Language: [Klingon](#) Project: [Interspeech2007](#) [\[Logout\]](#)

SPICE Project

You must do the following to build support for your language:

- [Text collection and selection](#)
- [Audio collection](#)
- [Phoneme set specification](#)
- [Lexicon pronunciation creation](#)
- [Speech recognition acoustic model creation](#)
- [Speech recognition language model creation](#)
- [Speech synthesis voice creation](#)

SPICE – System Functionalities

- SPICE Collects:
 - Appropriate text data
 - Appropriate audio data
- SPICE Defines and Refines:
 - Phoneme set
 - Rich prompt set
 - Lexical pronunciations
- SPICE Produces:
 - Vocabulary / Word lists (ASR, TTS, SMT)
 - Pronunciation model (ASR, TTS)
 - Acoustic model (ASR, TTS)
 - Language model (ASR, SMT)
 - Synthetic voices (TTS)
- SPICE Maintains:
 - Projects and users login
 - Data, Models, and Speech Processing Systems

Building Process

SPICE building process

1. Collect a text corpus
2. Generate a 200-1000 ut
3. Record the prompt list from one or more native speakers
4. Define a phoneme set
5. Construct a lexicon and letter-to-sound rules
6. Build a language model from the text corpus
7. Build acoustic models for ASR
8. Build voice models for TTS
9. Evaluate ASR and TTS using “talk-back” function

User: Sameer Language: Hindi Project: Sameer_Hindi [Logout]
Test acoustic model

क्या तुम्हे अच्छा लगता है

Sessions Panel

Speech-to-Text Text-to-Speech

Process Log

```
1. SUCCESS: Server path set to SameerHindi/Sameer_Hindi
2. SUCCESS: Language set to Hindi
3. SUCCESS: Server address set to plan.is.ts.cmu.edu:7090
4. SUCCESS: File uploaded: 68204 Bytes transferred.
5. SUCCESS: क्या तुम्हे अच्छा लगता है.
6. SUCCESS: Audio recorded successfully.
```

SPICE: Demo Tape

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Speech Processing Systems

Rapid Portability: Acoustic Models

Hello

Input: Speech

AM

hi /h//ai/
you /j//u/
we /w//i/

Lex

hi you
you are
I am

LM

NLP
/
MT

TTS

สวัสดี ครับ

Output:
Speech & Text

Rapid Portability: Pronunciation Dictionary

Hello
Input: Speech

สวัสดี ครับ
Output: Speech & Text

Rapid Portability: Language Modeling

Resource rich languages

Resource low languages

Focused Re-crawling

Bridge Languages

Text data

Hello

Input: Speech

สวัสดี ครับ

Output: Speech & Text

Bilingual LSA for Speech Translation

Multilingual Text and Speech Database

First step for studies on Multilingual Speech Processing
and language dependencies:
Collect large amounts of data in many languages
Project GlobalPhone (since 1995)

GlobalPhone

Multilingual Database

- Widespread languages
- Native Speakers
- Uniform Data
- Broad Domain
- Large Text Resources
 - Internet, Newspaper

Corpus

- 19 Languages ... counting
- ≥ 1800 native speakers
- ≥ 400 hrs Audio data
- Read Speech
- Filled pauses annotated

Arabic	Croatian	Turkish
Ch-Mandarin	Czech	+ Thai
Ch-Shanghai	Portuguese	+ Creole
German	Russian	+ Polish
French	Spanish	+ Bulgarian
Japanese	Swedish	+ ... ???
Korean	Tamil	

Available from ELRA

GlobalPhone Recognizers in 10 Languages

Rapid Portability: Acoustic Models

Rapid Portability: Data

Step 1:

- Uniform multilingual database (GlobalPhone)
- Build Monolingual acoustic models in many languages

Multilingual Acoustic Modeling

Step 2:

- Combine monolingual acoustic models to a set of multilingual “language independent” acoustic model

Universal Sound Inventory

Speech Production is independent from Language \Rightarrow IPA

1) IPA-based Universal Sound Inventory

2) Each sound class is trained by data sharing

- Reduction from 485 to 162 sound classes
- *m,n,s,l* appear in all 12 languages
- *p,b,t,d,k,g,f* and *i,u,e,a,o* in almost all

ML-Sep

ML-Mix

ML-Tag

Rapid Portability: Acoustic Models

Step 3:

- Define mapping between ML set and new language
- Bootstrap acoustic model of unseen language

Polyphone Decision Tree Adaptation

Problem:

Context of sounds are language specific
How to train context dependent models for new languages?

Solution:

- 1) Multilingual Decision Context Trees
- 2) Specialize decision tree by Adaptation

Rapid Portability: Acoustic Model

Word Error rate [%]

Rapid Portability: Pronunciation Dictionary

Hello
Input: Speech

สวัสดีครับ
Output: Speech & Text

Phoneme- vs Grapheme based ASR

Problem:

- 1 Grapheme \neq 1 Phoneme

Flexible Tree Tying (FTT):
One decision tree

- Improved parameter tying
- Less over specification
- Fewer inconsistencies

Dictionary: Interactive Learning

* Follow the work of Davel&Barnard

* Word list: extract from text

* G-2-P
- explicit map rules
- neural networks
- decision trees
- instance learning (grapheme context)

* Update after each w_i
→ effective training

User

Lex Learner

Build Your System

● Text and prompt selection (help)

● Audio collection (help)

● Phoneme selection (help)

● Grapheme-to-phoneme (help)

Phoneme labels for your language:

P B T D K G M

User: **awb** Language: **eng** Project: **aug19** [Logout]

Lexicon pronunciation creation

Rule entry

3.0075187969925% Finished

new word:

at

system suggested pronunciation: [listen to](#)

[it](#)

If you want to skip this word and work on it later, please click

If you don't think it's a valid word in your language, please click

Lex Learner

Build Your System

● Text and prompt selection (help)

● Audio collection (help)

● Phoneme selection (help)

● Grapheme-to-phoneme (help)

Phoneme labels for your language:

P B T D K G M

User: **awb** Language: **eng** Project: **aug19** [Logout]

Lexicon pronunciation creation

Rule entry

3.5087719298246% Finished

new word:

Jeanne

system suggested pronunciation: [listen to it](#)

If you want to skip this word and work on it later, please click

If you don't think it's a valid word in your language, please click

Issues and Challenges

- How to make best use of the human?
 - Definition of successful completion
 - Which words to present in what order
 - How to be robust against mistakes
 - Feedback that keeps users motivated to continue
- How many words to be solicited?
 - G2P complexity depends on the language (SP easy, EN hard)
 - 80% coverage
hundred (SP) to thousands (EN)
 - G2P rule system perplexity

Language	Perplexity
English	50.11
Dutch	16.80
German	16.70
Afrikaans	11.48
Italian	3.52
Spanish	1.21

Rapid Portability: TTS

Statistical Parametric TTS

- Text-to-speech for Applications, Common technologies:
 - Diphone: too hard to record and label
 - Unit selection: too much to record and label
- Statistical Parametric Synthesis: “just right”
 - “HMM synthesis”: **clustergen** trajectory synthesis
 - Clusters representing context-dependent allophones
 - Works robustly with as little as 10min speech data
 - But ... Signal may sound “buzzy”, can lack varied prosody
- Voice Building Process
 - Collect 300-500 utterances from single speaker, rich prompt set
 - Lexical coverage (from Lex Learner)
 - Automatic labeling from acoustic models
 - Automatic: spectral and prosodic models
- <http://festvox.org> [Black and Lenzo 2000]
 - Documentation, Tools, Scripts, Examples

TTS with very little Data

Rule of Thumb for getting the best gain per amount of labor

- ≤ 30 -60min speech: collect additional data
- > 60 min speech: improve lexicon

Mono vs. Multilingual Models

⇒ For all languages monolingual TTS performs best

⇒ Multilingual Models perform well ...

... only if knowledge about language is preserved (Multi+)
(only small amount of sharing actually happens)

Rapid Portability: Language Modeling

Language Model Building

Goal: Get as much relevant text data as possible

- Use the retrieved text data for
 - Generating recording prompts
 - Generating vocabulary lists
 - Build Language Models for ASR

Approach

1. User provides an URL or Text or Vocab list
2. Crawler retrieves N documents (web-pages)
3. Compute the statistics (TF-IDF) from the N documents
4. Terms with highest TF-IDF score form query terms
5. User may check terms for in/exclusion
6. Search engine (Google) gets URLs for the query terms
7. Crawl the top K URLs for the data

Case Study with very small data - Hindi

- Targeted Domain in Hindi: Cooking recipes
- Data: 192 sentences, 1,523 words = 13min speech, 1 spk
- Use speech to adapt multi-lingual acoustic models
- Use transcripts to build bigram LM1
- LM2: Expanded by focused re-crawling to 159,995 words
- LM3: Expanded to 360,395 words

- Three evaluation sets (spoken by same speaker)
⇒ Focused recrawling significantly reduces the OOV rate and thus WER

LM	word count	Word Error Rate (WER) (%) perplexity / OOV rate (%)			
		split 1	split 2	split 3	ave.
1	1523	95.88 5.2/68.7	97.92 6.9/57.9	84.93 7.8/50.0	92.91 6.6/58.9
2	159995	55.15 177/16.8	56.25 93.4/27.4	51.81 165/13.4	54.41 145/19.2
3	360395	54.12 214/15.0	52.08 113/25.0	50.60 187/11.3	52.27 171/17.1

SPICE 2005: Afrikaans – English

- Goal: Build Afrikaans – English Speech Translation System with SPICE
 - Cooperation with University Stellenbosch and ARMSCOR
 - Bilingual PhD visited CMU for 3 month
 - Afrikaans: Related to Dutch and English, g-2-p very close, regular grammar, simple morphology
- SPICE, all components apply statistical modeling paradigm
 - ASR: HMMs, N-gram LM (JRtk-ISL)
 - MT: Statistical MT (SMT-ISL)
 - TTS: Unit-Selection (Festival)
 - Dictionary: G-2-P rules using CART decision trees
- Text: 39 hansards; 680k words; 43k bilingual aligned sentence pairs; Audio: 6 hours read speech; 10k utterances, telephone speech (AST)

Time Effort

- Good results: ASR 20% WER; MT A-E (E-A) Bleu 34.1 (34.7), Nist 7.6 (7.9)
- Shared pronunciation dictionaries (for ASR+TTS) and LM (for ASR+MT)
- Most time consuming process: data preparation → reduce amount of data!
- Still too much expert knowledge required (e.g. ASR parameter tuning!)

SPICE 2007: Field Experiments

- Now targeting *more* languages in a *shorter* time frame
- 6-weeks Hands-on Course at CMU in Spring 2007
 - Adopt native languages of participating students as targets
 - Added up to 10 different languages: Bulgarian, English, French, German, Hindi, Konkani, Mandarin, Telugu, Turkish, Vietnamese
- Teams of two students with different native language
- Course goal was to build a simple S-2-S system and use this to communicate with each other in their mother tongue
 - Solely rely on SPICE tools
 - Build speech recognition components in two languages
 - Build simple SMT component in two directions
 - Build speech synthesis components in two languages
 - Report back on problems and system shortfalls

Schultz, T., Black, A., Badaskar, S., Hornyak, M., Kominek, J., *SPICE: Web-based Tools for Rapid Language Adaptation in Speech Processing Systems, Interspeech 2007, Antwerp.*

Field Experiments (2)

- The 10 languages cover broad range of peculiarities
- Writing system:
 - Logographic Hanzi (Mandarin);
 - Cyrillic (Bulgarian);
 - Roman (German, French and English);
 - phonographic segmental (Telugu and Hindi);
 - phonographic featural (Vietnamese)
 - No script: Konkani
- Segmentation: No segmentation (Chinese); Segmentation white spaces do not necessarily indicate word (Vietnamese)
- Morphology: simple, low inflecting (English), compounding (German), agglutinating (Turkish) ...
- Sound System: tonal (Mandarin and Vietnamese), stress (Bulgarian)
- G-2-P: straightforward (Turkish), challenging (Hindi), difficult (English), no relationship (Chinese), invented (Konkani)

Lessons Learned

- It is possible to create speech processing components for 10 languages in 6-weeks using SPICE
- Each language brings new challenges
- Many SPICE features turned out to be very helpful, e.g. only ONE speaker of Konkani in Pittsburgh, web recorder allowed remote collection of more speakers

- Log: time spent in SPICE interface
- Improve interface using breakdown
- Use feedback
- Interface allows for collaborative work

Task	Time Spent [hh:mm]
Text Collection	8:35
Audio Collection	10:07
Phoneme Selection	4:05
LM building	1:25
G-2-P specs	1:30

SPICE 2008: Cross-continental Course

- SPICE-based course between CMU and UKA
 - Students at Carnegie Mellon University, PA
 - Students at Karlsruhe University, Germany
 - Linked by weekly meeting over VC
- Similar to 2007 BUT distributed collaboration
 - Students create ASR & TTS in their native language
 - Bonus for the ambitious: train SMT systems and create a speech-to-speech translation system
- Evaluation includes
 - Time to complete
 - Task difficulties
 - ASR word error rate
 - TTS voice quality
- Fall 2008 course already in progress

Outline

- o The World's Languages
 - o 6900 languages – So what?
 - o Language Extinction – What can the community do about it?
 - o Do we need Speech Processing for all of them?
 - o Is this really science – not just retraining on a new language?
- o Language Characteristics
 - o Written form, scripts, letter-to-sound relationship
 - o Issues and Differences between languages
- o Challenges for Multilingual Speech Processing
 - o Lack of Resources (Money, Data, Technical Support)
 - o Lack of Experts
- o Solutions
 - o SPICE: A Rapid Language Adaptation Server
 - o Technologies: Leveraging off GlobalPhone & FestVox
 - o Experiments and Results
- o **Conclusions and Future Work**

Conclusions

- **Challenges in Multilingual Speech Processing**
 - Well defined build processes: ASR, MT, TTS ... BUT:
 - Every new language brings unseen challenges
 - Current (statistical) approaches require lots of data
 - ... and native language expert and technology expertise
 - How to bridge the gap between language and tech expert?
- **Proposed solution: SPICE**
 - Learning by interaction from a cooperative (but naïve) user
 - Rapid adaptation from language universal models
 - Knowledge sharing across components
 - Development cycle: Days rather than weeks

Next Steps

○ **Continuous Server Support**

- Improve Interface based on user feedback and lessons learned
- Improve Language Robustness: font encoding, ...
- Software Engineering, Scaling

○ **Collaboration**

- Multiple people working on the same project
- Leverage from archived projects

○ **Cross-confirmation**

- Multiple views for within and across project confirmation
- Confidence measure to find appropriate combination

○ **Error-blaming**

- End-to-end system Evaluation vs Component Evaluation
- Automatic Generation of Recommendations to improve systems

Try This At Home

- System is online at <http://cmuspice.org>
- Use system for your own project
 - Create new login/passwd and project
- Preloaded Hindi Example
 - Login as
 - Login: demo
 - Passwd: demo
 - Chose project # (your birth day)
- Book on ML Speech Processing
Elsevier, Academic Press, 2006

